

Highly sensitive detection of the neurodegenerative biomarker Tau by using the concentration effect of the pyro-electrohydrodynamic jetting

Concetta Di Natale^{a,b,*}, Sara Coppola^{a,b}, Veronica Vespini^b, Volodymyr Tkachenko^b, Simone Russo^a, Giuseppina Luciani^a, Giuseppe Vitiello^{a,c}, Francesca Ferranti^d, Silvia Mari^d, Pietro Ferraro^b, Pier Luca Maffettone^{a,b}, Simonetta Grilli^{a,b,**}

^a Dipartimento di Ingegneria Chimica, Dei Materiali e Della Produzione Industriale (DICMaPI), Università Degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, Piazzale Tecchio 80, 80125, Naples, Italy

^b Institute of Applied Sciences and Intelligent Systems (ISASI), National Research Council of Italy (CNR), Pozzuoli, NA, 80078, Italy

^c Center for Colloid and Surface Science (CSGI), Via Della Lastruccia, Sesto Fiorentino, FI, 80078, Italy

^d Agenzia Spaziale Italiana, Via Del Politecnico snc, 00133, Rome, Italy

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Biosensors
Neurodegeneration
Artificial urine
Tau protein
Pyro-electrohydrodynamics
P-jet

ABSTRACT

It is largely documented that neurodegenerative diseases can be effectively treated only if early diagnosed. In this context, the structural changes of some biomolecules such as Tau, seem to play a key role in neurodegeneration mechanism becoming eligible targets for an early diagnosis. Post-translational modifications are responsible to drive the Tau protein towards a transition phase from a native disorder conformation into a preaggregation state, which then straight recruits the final fibrillization process. Here, we show for the first time the detection of pre-aggregated Tau in artificial urine at femto-molar level, through the concentration effect of the pyro-electrohydrodynamic jet (p-jet) technique. An excellent linear calibration curve is demonstrated at the femto-molar level with a limit of detection (LOD) of 130 fM. Moreover, for the first time we show here the structure stability of the protein after p-jet application through a deep spectroscopic investigation. Thanks to the small volumes required and the relatively compact and cost-effective characteristics, this technique represents an innovative breakthrough in monitoring the early stage associated to neurodegeneration syndromes in different scenarios of point of care (POC) and such as for example in long-term human space exploration missions.

1. Introduction

The involvement of Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) production in neurodegeneration processes is now clear (Van Ombergen et al., 2017). In detail, abnormal ROS levels lead to oxidative cellular stress (OS), which trigger a deleterious effect on neuronal cells and can result in brain injury and multifunctional organ damage with an increased risk of age-related neurodegenerative diseases, such as Alzheimer's disease (AD) and Parkinson's disease (PD) (Mao et al., 2020). A hypothetical well studied mechanism for promotion of neurodegenerative disease by OS was based on protein folding and aggregation. In particular, it has been studied that, in response to ROS production, expression of some proteins in the hippocampus, such as β -synuclein, ubiquitin carboxy-terminal hydrolase L1 (UCHL1), pyruvate dehydrogenase or tubulin,

may result in enhanced protein aggregation, mitochondrial dysregulation or impairment of the cytoskeleton, leading to initiation of neurodegenerative diseases (Martirosyan et al., 2022; Zhou et al., 2020). To date, neurodegeneration diagnosis is based on the studies of protein structural changes but unfortunately most of these putative markers can be analysed only post-mortem by arduous radio-image analysis of different brain regions (Baldacci et al., 2020; Halperin et al., 2009). This evidence highlights the importance of detecting biomarkers in early phases of neurodegeneration. Indeed, it is widely recognized that whatever neurodegenerative syndrome can be effectively treated only if promptly diagnosed.

This necessity triggered intense research resulting in hundreds of putative biomarkers (e.g. blood levels of aggregated Tau or amyloid proteins) or diagnostic methods. Unfortunately, due to the complexity of

* Corresponding author. Dipartimento di Ingegneria Chimica, dei Materiali e della Produzione Industriale, Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II, Piazzale Tecchio 80, 80125, Naples, Italy.

** Corresponding author. Institute of Applied Sciences and Intelligent Systems (ISASI), National Research Council of Italy (CNR), Pozzuoli, NA, 80078, Italy
E-mail addresses: concetta.dinatale@unina.it (C. Di Natale), simonetta.grilli@cnr.it (S. Grilli).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2024.116234>

Received 5 December 2023; Received in revised form 29 February 2024; Accepted 20 March 2024

Available online 21 March 2024

0956-5663/© 2024 The Authors. Published by Elsevier B.V. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

plasma matrix, blood-based assays remain a challenge in the identification of peripheral biomarkers for a sensitive prompt diagnosis of neurodegenerative disorders (Elango et al., 2023). The field could benefit from analyzing biomarkers in other biofluids such as urine or saliva, which are more widely collectable through minimally invasive means, simpler to interpret, and performed on more routine diagnostic equipment (Santini et al., 2023).

In particular, the Tau protein biomarker belongs to the class of intrinsically disordered proteins (IDs) being characterized by the lack of a significant amount of secondary structure over a sequence of ~ 400 amino acids and a high solubility when free in solution (Skrabana et al., 2006). In AD and other Tauopathies, Tau forms insoluble fibrils derived by post-translational events (hyperphosphorylation, truncation) which led its transition phase from a disordered highly soluble protein to the insoluble aggregate. These modifications are presumed to change the native disorder of Tau firstly into a pre-aggregation state which then acquire a key role in the formation of the final fibrillization process (Boyko et al., 2019; Luna-Munoz et al., 2007; Wegmann et al., 2018).

In this study, we apply an innovative method based on what we call pyro-electrohydrodynamic jet (p-jet) for detecting the biomarker Tau in a pre-aggregation state down to femtomolar level, with a wide linear calibration range and extremely competitive values of the limit of detection (LOD) and of the limit of quantification (LOQ). The operation principle of this p-jet method is based on the use of the pyroelectric effect generated by ferroelectric crystals. The spontaneous polarization of the crystal can be changed by an appropriate temperature variation that, due to the pyroelectric effect, produces a non-negligible electric field associated to the unbalanced charges on the surface of the crystal. Thanks to its relatively high pyroelectric coefficient ($-8.3 \times 10^{-5} \text{ C m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$), the electric field generated in case of ferroelectric lithium niobate (LN) can reach significantly high values, up to about 14 kV/mm (Tkachenko et al., 2022). Our p-jet method uses this electric field to extract droplets with tiny volumes, down to tens of pL (Tkachenko et al., 2022), from a mother drop of the solution loaded in a stealth pin at a volume of $\sim 0.5 \mu\text{L}$. The technique is contact-free, and we already demonstrated that such tiny droplets can be accumulated to produce concentrated spots of fluorescent pre-labelled molecules with high reproducibility onto a solid glass slide (Itri et al., 2022; Rega et al., 2020).

Here, we apply the p-jet method to a more realistic case where we use a specific target protein which is of clinical interest, namely the Tau protein as biomarker of neurodegenerative diseases, and not pre-labelled but dissolved in a urine formulation that mimics the human urine. In this way we simulate the case of a clinician that aims at detecting low abundant Tau in human urine for early diagnosis purposes. It is well known that any assay procedure requires the calibration step. This is even more important here where we are proposing a new detection procedure. This involves the preparation of a set of standards containing a known amount of the analyte of interest and measuring the response for each standard. For this purpose, a set of known dilutions of Tau were spiked alongside the urine samples, and then immobilized into concentrated spots on a glass slide with a reactive epoxy surface. The controlled composition of the artificial human urine assured us the reliability of the standards, avoiding physiological variabilities (Clark et al., 2011; Sarigul et al., 2019; Taylor and Curhan, 2007). An immunofluorescence protocol was then applied to the spots to retrieve the calibration curve of the method, namely the behaviour of the fluorescence mean intensity as a function of the standards' concentrations. Recently (Di Natale et al., 2023), we presented the possibility to concentrate the Tau protein through the p-jet method but only very preliminary results were obtained therein. In fact, we just tested an immunofluorescence procedure for detecting Tau in the p-jet spots in case of relatively high concentrations, and we observed a concentration-dependent trend for the fluorescence signal with a LOD around 160 fM.

Here, we improved the p-jet method to achieve spots with a shorter diameter and hence with a higher concentration effect. This allowed us

to achieve a much more competitive LOD of 4 fM and a linear calibration curve in the range 4–640 fM. Moreover, here we perform for the first time a deep spectroscopic study on the Tau samples before and after the application of p-jet. The resulting data demonstrate that the thermal and the electrical stimuli applied during p-jet are negligible for the molecular structure of Tau, which remains unchanged. This is of fundamental importance for the accuracy of the immunoassay protocol that we applied to the p-jet spots. The results presented in this work open the route to the application of p-jet for high sensitive immunochemistry assays that could overcome the typical LOD encountered by conventional ELISA kits (Rega et al., 2020) in routine clinical procedures.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Reagents and materials

All chemicals as 2-(N-morpholino) ethanesulfonic acid (MES), sodium carbonate buffer, (hydroxymethyl)aminomethane (TRIS) were purchased by Merck/Sigma-Aldrich, Italy. Lithium niobate (LN) crystals were bought from Crystal Technology Inc. 2D. Epoxy activated glass slides were purchased from PolyAn GmbH, Germany. The pin is a commercial microarray stealth printing pin, SMP3, Arrayit Corporation. Elma Lab Clean N10 solution for pin washing was provided by VWR International, Radnor, Pennsylvania, United States. The rabbit anti-Tau derived from Cell Signaling Technologies Rabbit D1M9X (AlexaFluor 555 Conjugate) and the Tau protein by Tebubio S. r.l. The artificial human urine for real-world calibration was purchased from Biochemazone (code BZ325, Biodivision of Chemazone Inc., Alberta, Canada). According to the certificate of conformity of Biochemazone, this synthetic urine contains urea, creatinine, ions like chloride, sodium, potassium, calcium, sulphate, ammonium, phosphate, magnesium, and traces of human serum albumin, all in deionized water as solvent. The formulation is prepared in agreement with the composition reported in literature for the human urine of healthy people [Mayo Clinic MML. Rochester 2018 Test Catalog <https://www.mayocliniclabs.com/test-catalog> (2008); Putnam, 1971; Aitekenov et al., 2021]. Moreover, it contains 0.05% preservative according to most common methods of preservation for urine samples. In summary, this urine was ready-to-use and formulated according to official testing methods as well as to published research on the use of artificial urine www.biochemazone.com, thus mimicking human urine for characterizing new biosensing methods. Here, in fact, we propose a new assay procedure that requires a calibration procedure as illustrated later. This involves the preparation of a set of standards containing a known amount of the analyte of interest and measuring the response for each standard. For this purpose, a set of known dilutions of Tau were spiked alongside the urine samples. The controlled composition of the artificial human urine assured us the reliability of the standards, avoiding physiological differences (Clark et al., 2011; Sarigul et al., 2019; Taylor and Curhan, 2007).

2.2. CD measurements

The samples were prepared by dilution of freshly prepared Tau protein at 0.5 mg/mL using different buffer solutions: 10 mM 2-(N-morpholino)ethanesulfonic acid (MES) pH 5.5, 10 mM phosphate saline buffer (PBS) pH 7.5, 10 mM hydroxymethylaminomethane (TRIS) pH 8, 10 mM sodium carbonate pH 8.5 and artificial urine pH 6.5. Urine based samples were also evaluated before and after the p-jet deposition. CD spectra were recorded on a Jasco J-815 spectropolarimeter (JASCO, Tokyo, Japan) at 25 °C in the far-UV region from 190 to 260 nm in a 0.1 cm quartz cuvette. The other experimental settings were: 20 nm/min scan speed, 2.0 nm bandwidth, 0.2 nm resolution, 50 mdeg sensitivity and 4 s response. Each spectrum was obtained averaging three scans, subtracting contributions from the corresponding scans (Celetti et al., 2016; Di Natale et al. 2018, 2019, 2021b; Florio et al., 2021; La Manna et al. 2022a, 2022b). Deconvolutions of CD spectra were obtained by

BESTSEL software (<http://bestsel.elte.hu/>) (Vincenzi et al., 2022).

2.3. FTIR-ATR measurements

The structural changes of the Tau protein were studied at 0.5 mg/mL in different buffers (10 mM MES pH 5.5, 10 mM PBS pH 7.5, 10 mM TRIS pH 8, 10 mM sodium carbonate pH 8.5, artificial urine pH 6.5) before and after the p-jet deposition by FTIR-ATR. Understanding the protein secondary structure through spectral analysis is often complex. For instance, the amide I absorbance typically appears as a broad band in the spectrum, making it difficult to distinguish individual components. To overcome this challenge, various techniques such as contour analysis, band-narrowing methods, and curve fitting are employed to separate and identify overlapping bands in the spectrum. These methods are necessary to accurately resolve the complex nature of the amide I band and extract meaningful information about protein secondary structure. To avoid incorrect interpretations of protein's secondary structure, it was followed the protocol already proposed (Yang et al., 2015). IR spectra were gathered using 32 scans at a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} spanning a wavelength range of $4000\text{--}650\text{ cm}^{-1}$. From each spectrum, both background and water were subtracted to emphasize protein related bands. After the subtraction a baseline correction was performed, focusing over the region between 2000 cm^{-1} and 1300 cm^{-1} in which bands relative to amide I, amide II and amide III groups were shown (Di Natale et al. 2021a, 2022).

Once the spectra were adjusted, a second derivative analysis was run using a seven-points Savitzky–Golay derivative filtering, to split overlapping bands. This method was chosen since a key benefit of second-derivative analysis is that it can be done objectively without the need to select deconvolutional parameters arbitrarily. The second-derivative spectra were smoothed and inverted. After the second-derivative calculation, each spectrum was truncated in the range 1600 cm^{-1} and 1700 cm^{-1} (amide I region) and then peaks were fitted by utilizing nonlinear least squares. Gaussian curve fitting was initiated using the frequencies of the band centres which were seen in the second-derivative spectra in the amide I regions. The secondary content was determined by calculating the individual assigned band areas and their fraction of the total area in the amide I regions. In the second-derivative spectrum, the peak frequency of an absorbance remains the same as the original peak frequency, and the areas represent different types of secondary structures.

2.4. Immunodetection procedure

A mother solution of Tau in artificial human urine was prepared at a final concentration of 0.5 mg/mL in a slightly basic environment at pH 8.5, by mixing the human urine with 10 mM sodium carbonate at 1:10 ratio. Serial dilutions were then prepared as standards for retrieving the calibration curve (see Section 3.3). Such standard solutions were delivered by the p-jet on a glass slide with epoxy reactive surface to produce concentrated spots of the samples. The slide was then incubated

for 2 h at room temperature (RT) to allow the covalent bond of the Tau protein on the slide. In fact, the epoxy ring on the slide was activated by the slightly basic pH of the solution, allowing the NH_2 group of the Tau protein to bind covalently to the COOH group of the epoxy ring, as shown schematically in Fig. 1.

The slide was successively incubated with 3 mL of Arrayit Blocking solution (BlockIt Blocking buffer) for 1h at RT for saturating the free protein-binding sites. Then the slide was washed three times by Arrayit Washing Solution III for 5 min. A solution of primary antibody rabbit anti-Tau (AlexaFluor 555 Conjugate), with a volume of 3 mL at a dilution of 1:200, was added on the slide and incubated overnight at $4\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to allow its capture by the printed Tau protein spots thanks to their strong biomolecular recognition affinity to form a fluorescent antigen-antibody complex. Considering the complete composition of urine (see Section 2.1), the immunocomplex was generated under a realistic competitive reaction scheme, with the presence of albumin as interfering species in the detection of Tau. The washing steps were repeated, and the slide was dried by nitrogen gas and inserted in the microarray fluorescence scanner for the measurement of the spot intensities. Moreover, the stability of the p-jet spots was evaluated by recording the fluorescence signal after 7 days storage in a washing solution bath at RT.

2.5. Microarray scanner

The fluorescence image of the concentrated p-jet spots was recorded by a commercial confocal scanner (Innoscan710, Innopsys). A laser source at 532 nm was used for exciting the molecules in the spots, and two digital photomultipliers (PMT) for recording the optical signal emitted by the molecules. Adopted parameters were laser power 10 mW, scanning speed 10 lines/s, spatial resolution $3\text{ }\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$ and PMT gain 25%. The TIFF 16-bit images acquired by the scanner were analysed quantitatively by Mapix software to retrieve the mean value of the fluorescence signal in the spots.

2.6. Statistical analysis

The calibration curve of the assay was obtained by plotting the fluorescence intensity of the spots for each Tau protein concentration using GraphPad prism software, version 8 (Di Natale et al., 2020). The fluorescence intensity was retrieved as the average value over ten replicated spots for each protein concentration. The limit of detection (LoD) and the limit of quantification (LoQ) of the assay were based on the standard deviation (σ) of the response and the slope of the obtained calibration curve (s), following ICH's guidelines (Brown Jr, 2005), and are specified by the following equations:

$$LoD = \frac{3.3\sigma}{s}$$

$$LoQ = \frac{10\sigma}{s}$$

Fig. 1. Simplified view of the Tau covalent bond on the epoxy glass surface.

3. Results and discussion

In this study, we used the p-jet technique for producing what we call here concentrated “p-jet spots” of pre-aggregated Tau on the surface of a glass slide functionalized with epoxy groups, as illustrated schematically in the panel of Fig. 2.

Fig. 2(a) shows the general workflow of the technique from the formation of the spots till the fluorescence detection. The concentrated spots are formed by p-jet on an epoxy glass slide. The jetting process is monitored in real time by an optical path to control the number of the accumulated droplets on a single site. The slide with concentrated spots of highly diluted Tau is then taken from the p-jet setup and incubated at room temperature to favor the protein binding on the surface. Successively, it is incubated with the blocking solution to block the free reactive sites on the slide (see section 2.4 for further details about the immunodetection procedure). After appropriate washing steps the slide is incubated with a labelled primary antibody specific against the Tau protein. Thanks to the concentration effect of the p-jet procedure, the fluorescence signal measured by the scanner is highly significant and proportional to the Tau concentration, as explained in the following section 3.3.

Fig. 2(b) shows the magnified scheme of the formation of the concentrated spots by p-jet. The solution is loaded in the stealth microarray-printing pin by dipping. Under the pin, we have a tungsten wire, 300 μm thick, bent appropriately to get a nearly point-wise heat source in contact with the LN crystal (2×2) cm^2 sized. The wire and the crystal are kept fixed and aligned with the pin through a three-axes micrometric translation stage. The epoxy slide is mounted on another three-axes translation stage to stand in between the crystal and the pin and can be translated horizontally for printing different spots. In principle, the target slide may be functionalized with a specific chemistry, depending on the sample to be immobilized on.

The wire is heated by the Joule effect at constant time intervals, by applying a step function through a voltage generator. It is well known that temperature values exceeding 37 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ can cause detrimental effects on proteins and biomolecules in general (Zhao et al., 2022). Therefore, we measured the temperature of the surface of the target slide by an infrared camera under different settings of the step function and the best conditions used in this work are indicated in Table 1.

The LN crystal heats up to 35 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ in about 15 s, when subject to the

Table 1

Setting parameters of the step function applied to the heating wire.

Voltage (V)	Time on (s)	Time off (s)	Time total (s)
1.7	3.5	56.5	60

heating step and cools down to room temperature in about 15 s, as observed by a standard thermal imaging camera. This cycle of temperature variation generates the pyroelectric effect, and the intensity of the resulting electric field (see the field lines in Fig. 2(b)) is high enough to induce a charging effect on the free surface of the liquid meniscus emerging from the pin apex. The charged surface experiences a Coulomb repulsion, which overcomes the surface tension of the liquid up to the release of a liquid jet. Three jets were produced on average during one heating step. It is possible to apply different pulses to produce the desired number of jets.

The ejected droplets are observed sideways by a slow-motion camera (Motion Pro Y3-S1, IDT Corporation, pixel size of $10.85 \times 10.85 \mu\text{m}$), as illustrated schematically in Fig. 2(a). The droplet deposited on the slide experiences a slight evaporation, so that successive tiny droplets are accumulated on the same spot to enhance the number of molecules per unit area of reaction, by keeping fixed the position of the target slide. Here the concentrated spots were obtained by the accumulation of twenty droplets. The pin was cleaned after each spot by ultrasound bath in an appropriate washing solution (2% Elma commercial solution in distilled water) for 5 min. A series of different spots was obtained on the slide by replicating the p-jet procedure on a different position after X–Y translation. It is worth noting that, unlike the setup used in (Di Natale et al., 2023), here we changed the working distance between the tip of the pin and the slide surface to achieve a thinner bridge. Therefore, we obtained spots with a shorter diameter and hence with a higher concentration effect, which allowed us to reach a competitive LOD value as illustrated in section 3.3.

3.1. Spectroscopic investigation on the aggregation states of Tau

The analytical tool of circular dichroism (CD) spectroscopy was used to evaluate the aggregation states experienced by Tau in five different buffers, with increasing pH values. In detail, Tau CD spectra were recorded in solutions at 0.5 mg/mL concentration with the following

Fig. 2. Highly sensitive detection of Tau biomarker. (a) Schematic diagram of the workflow from the formation of the concentrated p-jet spots of highly diluted Tau to the detection of the fluorescence signal through the fluorescence scanner by using the immunodetection protocol that makes use of a labelled primary antibody against the Tau protein; (b) magnified scheme of the formation of the concentrated p-jet spots through the accumulation of tiny droplets ejected from the stealth pin by the electric field generated pyroelectrically in the LiNbO₃ crystal. The drawings are not to scale and there are only few spots drawn on the glass slide due to lack of space.

different conditions: (1) 10 mM MES at pH 5.5; (2) artificial urine at pH 6.5; (3) 10 mM PBS at pH 7.5; (4) 10 mM TRIS at pH 8.0; (5) 10 mM sodium carbonate at pH 8.5. As reported in Fig. 3(a), a typical aggregation spectrum with diagnostic minima at 217 nm, related to a β -sheet conformation, was recorded for the Tau protein dissolved in 10 mM PBS, 10 mM TRIS and 10 mM sodium carbonate. A lower signal is clearly visible in case of sodium carbonate and PBS, due to the formation of putative insoluble large aggregates. A typical CD spectrum of helical proteins with diagnostic minima at 208 nm and 222 nm were instead recorded for Tau in 10 mM MES and in artificial urine, underlying as slight acidic conditions lead the Tau protein towards a pre-aggregation state. These observations were confirmed by the CD deconvolution data reported in Table 2, where a high percentage of α -helix structure was retrieved for the Tau protein in MES and artificial urine, while a greater content of β -structure was recorded in case of basic conditions (\sim 60% for TRIS pH 8.0 and \sim 40% for PBS pH 7.5 and sodium carbonate pH 8.5).

A comparative study was carried out using the FTIR-ATR spectroscopic technique, and the corresponding spectra are reported in Fig. 3(b-f). Analogously to the CD results, the relative highest content of α -helix was retrieved for the Tau protein in MES (\sim 60%) and in artificial urine (\sim 40%), while a higher beta-sheet content (30–50%) was reported for the protein analysed in basic buffers. The deconvolution data were obtained by primary FTIR-ATR spectra, in which the peak related to Tau protein was confirmed by the presence of the characteristic protein band at 1653 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the amide I (mostly protein C=O stretching), as shown in Fig. 3(g).

A complete view of the spectroscopic characterization of Tau in different pH conditions is provided by Table 2. It reports the deconvolution data retrieved from the CD and FTIR-ATR spectra with the percentages of secondary structure exhibited by Tau in each solution, while Fig. 2(h) shows the schematic view of the transition phases experienced by the protein Tau from the native random state to fully aggregated stage during neurodegeneration processes.

The spectroscopic results reported in this section demonstrate clearly that a typical pre-aggregation state (α -helix conformation) is achieved *in vitro* for the Tau biomarker in case of acidic conditions, when dissolved in MES buffer and in artificial urine; it is in fact already reported that Tau aggregation phases are sensitive to pH and ionic conditions (Duan et al., 2023). These transition states, reproduced here, corresponds to the onset of the very first stages of the neurodegeneration pathology (Wegmann et al., 2018) and the traces detection in peripheral body fluids would be of great impact for early diagnosis applications.

3.2. Stability of Tau protein in the p-jet spots

The CD and FTIR-ATR spectroscopic techniques were used here for the first time for investigating the stability and the structural organization of a protein sample, more specifically the Tau protein, in the spots obtained by the p-jet technique. The sample solution pending from the microarray pin is subjected to a slight temperature increase and to a relatively high electric field, during the production of the tiny droplets by the pyroelectric effect. Therefore, the spectroscopic measurements can provide significant information about the impact of the pyroelectric effect on the structural conformation of the protein in the sample solution. This is of fundamental importance considering that the ability of p-jet to concentrate biomolecules (Itri et al., 2022) could have a disruptive application for highly sensitive detection of biomarkers only if the target molecules in the concentrated spots preserve their conformational structure for the successive reactions (e.g. immunofluorescence).

The protein Tau was dissolved in artificial urine at a concentration of 0.5 mg/mL. One aliquot was used for the measurement before p-jet, and another was loaded into the p-jet setup for producing ten replicates of spots onto the target slide. The sample from the p-jet spots was retrieved by loading approximately 1 μ L solution in the p-jet setup to obtain a relatively large sessile droplet on the slide that was taken manually by a

conventional pipette. Fig. 4(a) shows the resulting CD spectra. The blue curve refers to the sample solution just prepared, while the green curve reports the data recorded for the sample recovered from the p-jet spots.

These results clearly show that no conformational change was observed for the protein after the deposition of tiny droplets by the p-jet technique. In fact, the CD spectra recorded for the samples after p-jet (green curve) exhibit an α -helix trend that is identical to that of the just prepared sample, as confirmed by the deconvolution data displayed in Table 3.

Analogously, the FTIR-ATR measurements show how the deconvolution analyses reported a high percentage of α -helix structure before and after the p-jet, in agreement with the CD data, as shown in Fig. 4(b) and in Table 3. Also, in this case the deconvolution data were obtained by the primary FTIR-ATR spectra, by analysing the typical protein band at 1653 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the amide I (protein C=O stretching). It is noteworthy that the secondary structures of the Tau protein, which is generally sensitive to mechanical and/or electrical stress conditions, are preserved after generating the tiny droplets through the p-jet method (Duan et al., 2023). This aspect opens the route to a wider use of our p-jet method to more unstable molecules such as antibodies or DNA/mRNA.

3.3. Immunodetection of highly diluted Tau in the pre-aggregation state

The protein Tau was dissolved in artificial urine/sodium carbonate at the dilution ratio of 1/10 at a concentration of 0.5 mg/mL (see Section 2.1 for details about the urine and the reagents). This mother solution was then diluted appropriately to obtain a series of standard samples to be used for the immunodetection of pre-aggregated Tau in concentrated p-jet spots. First, we tested the technique in case of a relatively wide range of concentrations preparing solutions ranging from 0.16 pM up to 160 pM in both buffers. Ten aliquots of 0.5 μ L were retrieved from each sample and deposited on the target slide (i.e. epoxy activated glass slide) to obtain ten replicates of concentrated p-jet spots for each concentration. The slide was incubated for 2h at room temperature to favor the protein binding on the surface and then washed three times in the buffer solution, in agreement with the washing steps commonly required in immunoreaction protocols. Successively the slide was incubated in the blocking buffer and, subsequently, overnight with a fluorescent primary antibody. In the end, it was washed again to remove the excess of reagents and finally dried accurately by nitrogen gas.

The fluorescence image of the p-jet spots, produced by the immune complexes generated through the antigen-antibody reaction, was recorded by the scanner Innoscan710. In case of carbonate buffer, the fluorescence signal was recorded also after seven days bath in the buffer solution at room temperature. The mean intensity of the spots was retrieved by the Mapix software, and Fig. 5(a) shows the resulting data, where the intensity for each concentration is calculated as the mean value of the intensities measured over ten replicated spots. These data show how the signal intensity increases with the sample concentration in both buffers, thus demonstrating the reliability of the immunodetection on the p-jet spots on a relatively wide range of concentrations. In particular, the consistent behaviour in case of seven days bath demonstrates that, in perspective, the technique would be reliable in the market of lab on chip devices in terms of robustness, thanks to the stability of the signals even at room temperature and in humid environments. In fact, in case of common immunoassays like ELISA or chemiluminescent immunoassay (CLIA), the manufacturer rules often require storing the antibody pre-coated plates or microparticles at 2/8 °C together with a temperature-controlled supply chain from the transport to the final handling. This may not be reasonable in low-income countries with poor infrastructures where it is imperative to develop cooling-free technologies to provide stable and consistent bioassays (Kang et al., 2021). The p-jet technique would significantly improve the shelf-life and the stability of molecule-coated surfaces, thus increasing biomedical research and diagnostics to resource-limited

Fig. 3. Spectroscopic characterization of the Tau protein at a concentration of 0.5 mg/mL in five different buffers (PBS, TRIS, sodium carbonate, MES, urine) through (a) CD and (b-g) FTIR-ATR; (h) schematic view of the transition phases of Tau protein. The pH values measured for each solution is indicated by the labels in the graphs.

Table 2

Deconvolution data retrieved from the CD and FTIR-ATR spectra, reporting the percentage of Tau secondary structure for each buffer condition. The pre-aggregation state is underlined by % of α -helix composition.

% Secondary structure of Tau											
	MES pH 5.5		Artificial urine pH 6.5		PBS pH 7.5		TRIS pH 8.0		Sodium carbonate pH 8.5		
	CD	FTIR-ATR	CD	FTIR-ATR	CD	FTIR-ATR	CD	FTIR-ATR	CD	FTIR-ATR	
α -Helix	63.5	58.65	32.5	42.65	15.1	49.44	23.4	20.55	18.1	n.d.	
Beta sheet	13.9	33.49	23.6	13.94	36.7	36.68	67.4	49.03	41.1	28.28	
Turn	14.7	7.87	14.4	27.07	14.4	12.76	9.2	15.93	15.4	21.28	
Others	8.0	n.d.	29.5	16.34	33.6b	18.02	0.0	14.48	25.5	50.36	

Fig. 4. Spectroscopic characterization of the Tau stability in the p-jet spots by (a) CD, (b) FTIR/ATR deconvolution.

Table 3

Deconvolution data retrieved from the CD and FTIR-ATR spectra, reporting the percentage of secondary structure for the Tau protein dissolved in artificial urine (pH 6.5) and recorded before and after the p-jet deposition.

	CD		FTIR-ATR	
	Before p-jet	After p-jet	Before p-jet	After p-jet
α -Helix	32.5	35.8	42.65	55.93
Beta sheet	23.6	20.6	13.94	16.03
Turn	14.4	15.2	27.07	23.71
Others	29.5	28.5	16.34	4.32

settings. Moreover, the p-jet ability to maintain the structural integrity and the functionality of proteins after many days being immobilized to the solid surface is a very promising result since immobilization of biomolecules are often the critical step in bioassay performance as sensitivity and specificity. In fact, after being coated to the reactive surface (e.g. ELISA plate, polymeric or glass surfaces), they are particularly inclined to lose their conformation and so their affinity to antigens under room temperature conditions (Gauglitz, 2020).

Moreover, the greater signal of the protein at the same concentration in urine compared to carbonate buffer, corroborates the spectroscopic data, highlighting how in an acidic environment Tau is in a more open conformation and therefore available for the antibody binding. These data also indicate that our method could be used to analyze the different conformations of the Tau protein as function of the degree of neurodegeneration progression.

The same experiment was performed by depositing the same volume (0.5 μ L) of each sample solution in a single droplet by a standard pipette, obtaining ten replicates of droplets on the target slide that we call in brief “manual spots”. Fig. 5(b) shows the resulting behaviour of the mean fluorescence intensity. The dashed line corresponds to the level of background plus three times the standard deviation of the background intensity. Even though a slight increase of the signal is detected for the

manual spots, the signal is clearly meaningless in the sub-picomolar level, thus demonstrating the concentration effect produced by the p-jet technique through the accumulation of tiny droplets produced from the same 0.5 μ L starting volume.

Successively, we focused our attention on the performance of the p-jet spots in a more challenging range, namely down to sub-picomolar level. Hence, we prepared highly diluted samples of pre-aggregated Tau in artificial urine, down to 4 fM. Ten replicates of p-jet spots were obtained for each solution and the same immunoassay protocol described above was applied to the glass slide. Ten replicates of p-jet spots were produced also with the artificial urine buffer on the same slide, as negative control. The fluorescence intensity of the spots, subtracted by the negative control, is reported in Fig. 5(c).

The signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) was >4 for all the spots, thus demonstrating that a significant signal is obtained down to 4 fM concentration. The signal increases clearly with the concentration of the sample solution and an excellent linear trend is found in the range 4 fM – 640 fM, with a coefficient of determination $r^2 = 0.99$. Very competitive values of LOD and LOQ, respectively 130 fM and 390 fM, were retrieved by the statistical analysis of the fluorescence data (see the **Experimental section** for details). It is noteworthy that the SNR in the spots with negative control was <2 on average.

The inset in Fig. 5(c) shows the typical scanner images of the concentrated p-jet spots in the sub-picomolar range, just as an example, corresponding to the sample standard concentrations in the graph in (c). In particular, the concentration of the spots increases from left to right and the diameter was 300 μ m on average. It is important to note that when an image is acquired by the scanner the pixel depth is 16 bits, while on-screen images are only displayed with an 8-bit pixel depth, due to hardware limitations of standard graphic boards. Therefore, the intensity gradation is not always distinguishable on the screen. For example, the intensity of the last two spots on the right (inset of Fig. 5(c)) look similar but the pixel depth values retrieved by Mapix show the increasing trend (graph in Fig. 5(c)). Fig. 5(d) reports the typical

Fig. 5. Immunodetection of pre-aggregated Tau in concentrated p-jet spots of urine-based samples. Behaviour of the mean fluorescence of the spots in case of (a) concentrated p-jet spots in a wide range of concentrations in different buffers and after seven days bath, (b) manual spots and (c) concentrated p-jet spots in the sub-picomolar range with linear trend in the range 4–640 fM; (d) typical intensity profile of the p-jet spots analysed in (c). The inset in (c) shows the typical scanner images of the spots corresponding to the standard samples in the graph in (c) and, specifically, with concentration increasing from left to right. The average spot diameter was 300 μm. The spot intensities were retrieved as mean values over ten replicates and the error bars correspond to the \pm standard deviation.

intensity profiles of the spots at the serial concentrations. These data show the distribution of the signal in the spots with a significant level of homogeneity over a diameter that is around 300 μm on average.

Considering that the urine used here has a complete composition, resembles the real human urine and contains also traces of human serum albumin (see Section 2.1), these results demonstrate the specificity and the reliability of the technique in case of a complex matrix like the human urine. This opens the route for a future application of our technique in a real-world assay relatively easy to accomplish. In fact, the real samples of urine collected from volunteers and/or patients will need simply to be mixed with sodium carbonate to adjust the pH to 8.5 for the covalent bond and will be purified by eventual residual blood cells and/or bacteria by standard procedures prior to p-jet.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, we used the p-jet technique to concentrate tiny droplets of pre-aggregated Tau samples on the surface of a reactive glass slide. For the first time we applied an immunoreaction procedure onto the p-jet spots, and we achieved a highly sensitive detection of pre-aggregated Tau spiked in standard samples of artificial human urine. An excellent linear calibration curve was obtained in the sub-picomolar range and with a LOD of 130 fM. These results are of great interest in the field of clinical assays, considering the typical LOD values provided by routine immunoassay kits (Lifke et al., 2019; Yamamori et al., 2007), as also described in the Supplementary Material. Moreover, such successful detection was obtained in artificial urine that resembles the composition of real human urine, a body fluid that is very easy to collect, thus pushing the p-jet technique towards a more realistic application for the development of a highly sensitive device for early diagnosis purposes. In fact, in case of the Alzheimer's disease, the ability to detect traces of pre-aggregated Tau in a peripheral body fluid, such as urine, would have a disruptive impact for the early diagnosis. The prodromes of the disease would be recognized before the occurrence of irreversible effects and, moreover, avoiding invasive withdrawal of the cerebrospinal fluid as occurring in routine clinical procedures.

Over the years, researchers have followed different techniques to improve biomarker detection, including the amplification of the target molecules. Here, we address this demand for sensitivity increase in diagnostic neurodegeneration assays through preconcentration of target molecules by a sort of solvent removal. Our approach drastically increases the biomarker concentration by reducing the reaction volume (down to sub-microliter) through the accumulation of tiny droplets of the liquid body fluid onto a solid support (e.g. glass reactive slide) before the immunodetection procedure. In other words, we achieved an amplification of the signal by limiting drastically the diffusion effects with the result of a highly competitive LOD.

In perspective, we believe that the proposed method, due to its relatively compact and cost-effective characteristics and the small volumes of sample, could represent an innovative tool for detecting and monitoring the very early stage of neuro-degeneration syndromes, even in different scenarios such as POC applications in human space missions. Indeed, it is mainly documented that the involvement of microgravity in the excessive reactive oxygen species (ROS) production contributes to oxidative cellular stress and multifunctional damage in astronaut with an increase in development of age-related neurodegenerative diseases, such as AD and Parkinson's disease (Mao et al., 2020). In detail, neurons are predisposed to degenerate under microgravity, and cosmic radiation amplifying neurodegeneration mechanisms (Mao et al., 2020). For example, spaceflight impairs vestibular function, influencing cognition, and other biological processes which are usually present in AD patients (Clément et al., 2020). In the modern context, which foresees the possibility of prolonged stays in space, our revolutionary approach could be extremely useful for monitoring the health of astronauts, intervening promptly with a highly sensitive diagnosis.

In summary, the possibility to detect neurodegenerative-related biomarkers through a simple urine test, would set new standards for neurodegeneration screening in the population. Moreover, it is awaited to improve patient compliance and follow-up during therapy. It is notable that the application of our technique is not restricted to neurodegeneration but it can be implemented for the detection of other low-abundance disease-related biomarkers.

ORCID iD authorship contribution statement

Concetta Di Natale: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sara Coppola:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Investigation, Data curation. **Veronica Vespini:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Investigation. **Volodymyr Tkachenko:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Validation, Investigation, Formal analysis. **Simone Russo:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation. **Giuseppina Luciani:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision. **Giuseppe Vitiello:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Methodology. **Francesca Ferranti:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Silvia Mari:** Writing – review & editing, Validation. **Pietro Ferraro:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Pier Luca Maffettone:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition. **Simonetta Grilli:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors state that they are not aware of any financial or inter-personal conflicts that might have appeared to have an impact on the research presented in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge the EU funding within the Horizon 2020 Program, under the FET-OPEN Project SensApp, Grant Agreement n.829104. This research was funded by the Italian collaborative agreement between the Italian Space Agency (ASI) and the University of Naples “Federico II” n. 2021-20-HH.0 on “Innovative Health Technology Development Activities in Space”, Italian project code F65F21000830005.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bios.2024.116234>.

References

- Aitekenov, Sultan, Gaipov, Abdzhappar, Bukasov, Rostislav, 2021. Review: Detection and quantification of proteins in human urine. *Talanta* 223, 121718.
- Baldacci, F., Mazzucchi, S., Della Vecchia, A., Giampietri, L., Giannini, N., Koronyo-Hamaoui, M., Ceravolo, R., Siciliano, G., Bonuccelli, U., Elahi, F.M., 2020. The path to biomarker-based diagnostic criteria for the spectrum of neurodegenerative diseases. *Expert Rev. Mol. Diagn.* 20 (4), 421–441.
- Boyko, S., Qi, X., Chen, T.-H., Surewicz, K., Surewicz, W.K., 2019. Liquid–liquid phase separation of tau protein: the crucial role of electrostatic interactions. *J. Biol. Chem.* 294 (29), 11054–11059.
- Brown Jr., R.S., 2005. Hepatitis C and liver transplantation. *Nature* 436 (7053), 973–978.
- Celetti, G., Di Natale, C., Causa, F., Battista, E., Netti, P.A., 2016. Functionalized poly (ethylene glycol) diacrylate microgels by microfluidics: in situ peptide encapsulation for in serum selective protein detection. *Colloids Surf. B Biointerfaces* 145, 21–29.
- Clark, W.F., Sontrop, J.M., Macnab, J.J., Suri, R.S., Moist, L., Salvadori, M., Garg, A.X., 2011. Urine volume and change in estimated GFR in a community-based cohort study. *Clin. J. Am. Soc. Nephrol.: CJASN* 6 (11), 2634.
- Clément, G.R., Boyle, R.D., George, K.A., Nelson, G.A., Reschke, M.F., Williams, T.J., Paloski, W.H., 2020. Challenges to the central nervous system during human spaceflight missions to Mars. *J. Neurophysiol.* 123 (5), 2037–2063.
- Di Natale, C., Battista, E., Lettera, V., Reddy, N., Pitingolo, G., Vecchione, R., Causa, F., Netti, P.A., 2021a. Easy surface functionalization and bioconjugation of peptides as

- capture agents of a microfluidic biosensing platform for multiplex assay in serum. *Bioconjugate Chem.* 32 (8), 1593–1601.
- Di Natale, C., Celetti, G., Scognamiglio, P.L., Cosenza, C., Battista, E., Causa, F., Netti, P. A., 2018. Molecularly endowed hydrogel with an in silico-assisted screened peptide for highly sensitive small molecule harvesting. *Chem. Commun.* 54 (72), 10088–10091.
- Di Natale, C., Coppola, S., Vespini, V., Tkachenko, V., Luciani, G., Vitiello, G., Maffettone, P.L., Grilli, S., Mari, S., Ferranti, F., 2023. Development of an innovative biosensor for testing picogram level of the Tau protein involved in microgravity associated neurodegeneration. In: 2023 IEEE 10th International Workshop on Metrology for AeroSpace (MetroAeroSpace), pp. 162–165. IEEE.
- Di Natale, C., De Gregorio, V., Lagreca, E., Mauro, F., Corrado, B., Vecchione, R., Netti, P. A., 2022. Engineered bacterial cellulose nanostructured matrix for incubation and release of drug-loaded oil in water nanoemulsion. *Front. Bioeng. Biotechnol.* 10.
- Di Natale, C., De Rosa, D., Profeta, M., Jamaledin, R., Attanasio, A., Lagreca, E., Scognamiglio, P.L., Netti, P.A., Vecchione, R., 2021b. Design of biodegradable bi-compartmental microneedles for the stabilization and the controlled release of the labile molecule collagenase for skin healthcare. *J. Mater. Chem. B* 9 (2), 392–403.
- Di Natale, C., La Manna, S., Malfitano, A.M., Di Somma, S., Florio, D., Scognamiglio, P.L., Novellino, E., Netti, P.A., Marasco, D., 2019. Structural insights into amyloid structures of the C-terminal region of nucleophosmin 1 in type A mutation of acute myeloid leukemia. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta Protein Proteomics* 1867 (6), 637–644.
- Di Natale, C., Onesto, V., Lagreca, E., Vecchione, R., Netti, P.A., 2020. Tunable release of curcumin with an in silico-supported approach from mixtures of highly porous PLGA microparticles. *Materials* 13 (8), 1807.
- Duan, P., Dregni, A.J., Mammeri, N.E., Hong, M., 2023. Structure of the nonhelical filament of the Alzheimer’s disease tau core. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. USA* 120 (44), e2310067120.
- Elango, R., Banaganapalli, B., Mujalli, A., AlRayes, N., Almaghrabi, S., Almansouri, M., Sahly, A., Jadhkarim, G.A., Malik, M.Z., Kutbi, H.I., 2023. Potential biomarkers for Parkinson disease from functional enrichment and bioinformatic analysis of global gene expression patterns of blood and substantia nigra tissues. *Bioinf. Biol. Insights* 17, 11779322231166214.
- Florio, D., Di Natale, C., Scognamiglio, P.L., Leone, M., La Manna, S., Di Somma, S., Netti, P.A., Malfitano, A.M., Marasco, D., 2021. Self-assembly of bio-inspired heterochiral peptides, 114, 105047.
- Gauglitz, G., 2020. Critical assessment of relevant methods in the field of biosensors with direct optical detection based on fibers and waveguides using plasmonic, resonance, and interference effects. *Anal. Bioanal. Chem.* 412, 3317–3349.
- Halperin, I., Morelli, M., Korczyn, A.D., Youdim, M.B., Mandel, S.A., 2009. Biomarkers for evaluation of clinical efficacy of multipotential neuroprotective drugs for Alzheimer’s and Parkinson’s diseases. *Neurotherapeutics* 6, 128–140.
- Itri, S., del Giudice, D., Mugnano, M., Tkachenko, V., Uusitalo, S., Kokkonen, A., Pääkkilä, I., Ottevaere, H., Nie, Y., Mazzon, E., 2022. A pin-based pyro-electrohydrodynamic jet sensor for tuning the accumulation of biomolecules down to sub-picogram level detection. *Sensing and Bio-Sensing Research* 38, 100536.
- Kang, L., Smith, S., Wang, C., 2021. Stabilization of surface-bound antibodies for ELISA based on a reversible zeolitic imidazolate framework-8 coating. *J. Colloid Interface Sci.* 588, 101–109.
- La Manna, S., Florio, D., Panzetta, V., Roviello, V., Netti, P.A., Di Natale, C., Marasco, D., 2022a. Hydrogelation tunability of bioinspired short peptides. *Soft Matter* 18 (44), 8418–8426.
- La Manna, S., Leone, M., Iacobucci, I., Annuziata, A., Di Natale, C., Lagreca, E., Malfitano, A.M., Ruffo, F., Merlino, A., Monti, M., 2022b. Glucosyl platinum (II) complexes inhibit aggregation of the C-terminal region of the A β peptide. *Inorg. Chem.* 61 (8), 3540–3552.
- Lifke, V., Kollmorgen, G., Manuilova, E., Oelschlaegel, T., Hillringhaus, L., Widmann, M., von Arnim, C.A.F., Otto, M., Christenson, R.H., Powers, J.L., Shaw, L.M., Hansson, O., Doecke, J.D., Li, Q.-X., Teunissen, C., Tuman, H., Blennow, K., 2019. Elecsys® Total-Tau and Phospho-Tau (181P) CSF assays: analytical performance of the novel, fully automated immunoassays for quantification of tau proteins in human cerebrospinal fluid. *Clin. Biochem.* 72, 30–38.
- Luna-Munoz, J., Chavez-Macias, L., Garcia-Sierra, F., Mena, R., 2007. Earliest stages of tau conformational changes are related to the appearance of a sequence of specific phospho-dependent tau epitopes in Alzheimer’s disease. *J. Alzheimer. Dis.* 12 (4), 365–375.
- Mao, X.W., Nishiyama, N.C., Byrum, S.D., Stanbouly, S., Jones, T., Holley, J., Sridharan, V., Boerma, M., Tackett, A.J., Willey, J.S., 2020. Spaceflight induces oxidative damage to blood-brain barrier integrity in a mouse model. *Faseb. J.: official publication of the Federation of American Societies for Experimental Biology* 34 (11), 15516.
- Martirosyan, A., Falke, S., McCombs, D., Cox, M., Radka, C.D., Knop, J., Betzel, C., DeLucas, L.J., 2022. Tracing transport of protein aggregates in microgravity versus unit gravity crystallization. *npj Microgravity* 8 (1), 4.
- Putnam, D.F., 1971. Composition and concentrative properties of human urine. *NASA Contractor Reports*.
- Rega, R., Mugnano, M., Oleandro, E., Tkachenko, V., Del Giudice, D., Bagnato, G., Ferraro, P., Grilli, S., Gangemi, S., 2020. Detecting collagen molecules at picogram level through electric field-induced accumulation. *Sensors* 20 (12), 3567.
- Santini, D., Botticelli, A., Galvano, A., Iuliani, M., Incorvaia, L., Gristina, V., Taffon, C., Foderaro, S., Paccagnella, E., Simonetti, S., 2023. Network approach in liquidomics landscape. *J. Exp. Clin. Cancer Res.* 42 (1), 193.
- Sarigul, N., Korkmaz, F., Kurultak, I., 2019. A new artificial urine protocol to better imitate human urine. *Sci. Rep.* 9 (1), 20159.

- Skrabana, R., Sevcik, J., Novak, M., 2006. Intrinsically disordered proteins in the neurodegenerative processes: formation of tau protein paired helical filaments and their analysis. *Cell. Mol. Neurobiol.* 26, 1083–1095.
- Taylor, E.N., Curhan, G.C., 2007. Differences in 24-hour urine composition between black and white women. *J. Am. Soc. Nephrol.* 18 (2), 654–659.
- Tkachenko, V., Schwödiauer, R., Rega, R., Itri, S., Mugnano, M., del Giudice, D., Ottevaere, H., Nie, Y., Ferraro, P., Grilli, S., 2022. High-rate accumulation of tiny aqueous droplets using a pyroelectrohydrodynamic jet system. *Adv. Eng. Mater.* 24 (3), 2100756.
- Van Ombergen, A., Demertzi, A., Tomilovskaya, E., Jeurissen, B., Sijbers, J., Kozlovskaya, I.B., Parizel, P.M., Van de Heyning, P.H., Sunaert, S., Laureys, S., 2017. The effect of spaceflight and microgravity on the human brain. *J. Neurol.* 264, 18–22.
- Vincenzi, M., Mercurio, F.A., Di Natale, C., Palumbo, R., Pirone, L., La Manna, S., Marasco, D., Pedone, E.M., Leone, M., 2022. Targeting Ship2-Sam with peptide ligands: novel insights from a multidisciplinary approach. *Bioorg. Chem.* 122, 105680.
- Wegmann, S., Eftekharzadeh, B., Tepper, K., Zoltowska, K.M., Bennett, R.E., Dujardin, S., Laskowski, P.R., MacKenzie, D., Kamath, T., Commins, C., 2018. Tau protein liquid–liquid phase separation can initiate tau aggregation. *EMBO J.* 37 (7), e98049.
- Yamamori, H., Khatoon, S., Grundke-Iqbal, I., Blennow, K., Ewers, M., Hampel, H., Iqbal, K., 2007. Tau in cerebrospinal fluid: a sensitive sandwich enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay using tyramide signal amplification. *Neurosci. Lett.* 418 (2), 186–189.
- Yang, H., Yang, S., Kong, J., Dong, A., Yu, S., 2015. Obtaining information about protein secondary structures in aqueous solution using Fourier transform IR spectroscopy. *Nat. Protoc.* 10 (3), 382–396.
- Zhao, L., Zhao, J., Zhong, K., Tong, A., Jia, D., 2022. Targeted protein degradation: mechanisms, strategies and application. *Signal Transduct. Targeted Ther.* 7 (1), 113.
- Zhou, J., Ruggeri, F.S., Zimmermann, M.R., Meisl, G., Longo, G., Sekatskii, S.K., Knowles, T.P., Dietler, G., 2020. Effects of sedimentation, microgravity, hydrodynamic mixing and air–water interface on α -synuclein amyloid formation. *Chem. Sci.* 11 (14), 3687–3693.